

A Reproducibility study on the paper Comparing Intrinsic and Extrinsic Evaluation of Sensitivity Classification

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This study examines the reproducibility of Comparing Intrinsic and Extrinsic Evaluation of Sensitivity Classification [M. F. Sayed et al. 2022]. While we successfully replicated the intrinsic evaluation results using the OHSUMED dataset, the extrinsic evaluation showed significant discrepancies due to missing methodological details. Our findings highlight the need for more transparent reporting to improve reproducibility in machine learning research.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility, Sensitivity Classification, Intrinsic Evaluation, Extrinsic Evaluation

1 Introduction

Reproducibility has been an emerging field over the last years and has become an important criterion for new publications. A recent ACM study [Collberg and Proebsting 2016] analyzed the reproducibility of 613 conference papers. They found that only a fraction of published papers actively address reproducibility. This is an issue, since non-reproducible results can hinder further research on a particular topic and lead to misleading evidence. Reproducibility studies can validate and strengthen the results of a paper significantly reducing the risk of false positives. This study aims to address this problem by attempting to reproduce the results of the paper Comparing Intrinsic and Extrinsic Evaluation of Sensitivity Classification [M. F. Sayed et al. 2022].

The original paper describes a novel approach to classify sensitive information. They use 2 datasets on which they perform intrinsic and extrinsic evaluation of sensitivity classification. This topic is of great interest, as more and more technological applications have to deal with this problem as manual differentiation is no longer possible anymore due to the huge amount of data.

This paper is structured in the following sections: the methods section describes the methods of the original paper - intrinsic and extrinsic evaluation. In the next section, we present our reproducibility pipeline, which describes the steps we took to reproduce the paper. Furthermore, we analyze whether important information for reproduction is missing or unclear and how this can be addressed. In the results section, we analyze whether our results are consistent with the results of the original paper regarding the intrinsic and extrinsic evaluation. Then we check the statistical relevance of our results. Finally, a discussion section concludes this study by addressing the difficulties encountered and why our results may differ from the original paper.

2 Methodology of Source Paper

The original paper [M. F. Sayed et al. 2022] proposes a novel approach of combining Logistic Regression (LR) and neural DistilBERT models to predict sensitivity labels of text data. The datasets used are Avocado [Oard et al. 2015] and OSHUMED [Hersh et al. 1994]. However, as we were

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unable to obtain the Avocado dataset, we only perform our analysis on the OSHUMED dataset and focus on the methods applied to it.

More precisely, based on what we know from the paper we aim to reproduce [M. F. Sayed et al. 2022] and its cited references, they tested three different models on the sensitivity classification task: LR, DistilBERT, and an ensemble model. The tests were performed on the OHSUMED dataset. All of the documents are sensitivity-labeled, but a subset of them also has relevance labels. To construct a test set, they selected documents with sensitivity and relevance labels. The remaining documents that had sensitivity labels but no relevance labels, were split into 85% for training the sensitivity classifiers and 15% for validation to optimize classifier hyper-parameters.

The first model implemented is a logistic regression classifier using the sklearn library called LogisticRegression; it was trained on the title and abstract of each document in the OHSUMED dataset. Each document was represented as a TF-IDF vector incorporating unigrams and bigrams (this information wasn't explicit in the original paper but was available in [M. Sayed and Oard 2019]). The hyperparameters associated with the tokenization (whether to use only unigrams or both unigrams and bigrams) and the maximum number of features were optimized by a grid search with 5-fold cross-validation on the training set. In addition, the probability threshold for classification was optimized with the goal of maximizing the F1-score on the validation set.

The second model was a neural classifier, being based on the Huggingface's DistilBERT pre-trained transformer model for efficient text classification. The authors fine-tuned this model using the OHSUMED training set, with the input text tokenized into word embeddings and truncated to the model's 512-token limit.

The last model was a disjunctive combination of logistic regression and DistilBERT, classifying a document as sensitive if either model labeled it as such. The authors evaluated model performance using several metrics: precision, defined as the proportion of predicted sensitive documents that were actually sensitive; recall, defined as the proportion of actual sensitive documents that were correctly identified; F1-score, which represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall; and F2-score, a variant of F1-score that assigns greater weight to recall.

3 Reproducibility Pipeline

3.1 Data Acquisition

In terms of data availability, we faced the problem that the avocado dataset is not publicly available for free and not available to our institution. Therefore, due to lack of funds, we were not able to get this dataset. Thus, we had to limit our reproducibility study to the OHSUMED dataset. In the following sections we describe how we carried out each step of our pipeline. As the data source was not cited in the paper, an intensive web search led us to the original OHSUMED dataset [Hersh et al. 1994]. As this dataset itself does not contain any sensitivity nor any relevance labels, we had to perform several preprocessing steps. All methods were implemented in Python3 [Foundation 2025].

3.2 Data Preprocessing

As the sensitivity and relevance labels are crucial for both the data splitting and the evaluations, we had to search for ways to get these labels. Much of the necessary information was not given in the original paper, but in one of the papers cited by the authors [M. Sayed and Oard 2019]. For the relevance labels, we had to find the document which contained all the judged document IDs and map the judgments to the according documents.

Creating the ground truth sensitivity labels was more complex, as we only had the title and abstract of each entry. The sensitivity labeling was based on MeSH-terms (Medical Subject Headings) for sensitive health topics, specifically of the MeSH-categories C12 and C13. As the paper is from 2019 these categories are outdated by now so we had to look for the terms from 2019. After obtaining them [Medicine 2019] we needed to search for these terms in all abstracts and titles and then managed to get approximately the same amount of content labeled as sensitive as they did in the paper.

As we do not have the original dataset used in the paper, we can not tell whether this approach resulted in exactly the same sensitivity labeling for each row, which can also lead to differences in experimental outcomes.

3.3 Reproduction of the Intrinsic Results

3.3.1 Logistic Regression. The implementation of the logistic regression model was not entirely straightforward. Due to insufficient detail in the original paper, we consulted additional references cited within it to clarify certain aspects of the model. While the division of the training, validation, and test sets was clearly described, the absence of a specified random seed prevented exact replication of the authors' results.

Moreover, the optimization of tokenization hyperparameters was only briefly discussed in the original paper, with additional details found in further references [M. Sayed and Oard 2019]. However, the exact set of hyperparameters tested in the grid search was not explicitly provided. As a result, we selected key parameters, such as the maximum number of features and whether to include only unigrams or both unigrams and bigrams, based on reasonable assumptions. The optimal results in terms of F1 were obtained without setting a limit on the maximum number of features and considering both unigrams and bigrams.

The approach for determining the decision threshold exploiting the validation set in the logistic regression model was well explained. However, given that the authors proposed a threshold value of 0.84 and that the dataset exhibited a class imbalance favoring the negative class (0), we initially expected a lower threshold to be optimal. This suggested the possible use of compensatory techniques to mitigate class imbalance. To account for this, we applied a weighting system in our implementation. This method assigns weights to classes inversely proportional to their frequencies in the training data, thereby adjusting for the imbalance. Using this approach, we obtained a threshold value of 0.66, which is closer to the threshold reported by the authors.

3.3.2 DistilBERT. As mentioned in the paper, we used huggingface's DistilBERT to perform the sensitivity classification. To be able to parse the documents in DistilBERT, we tokenized them. The dataset was then used to train the model and to optimize the threshold for sensitivity classification towards the F1-score, as mentioned in the paper. As the paper did not provide a random seed or specific training arguments for the implementation, we had to choose our own.

Training and prediction with DistilBERT took a long time and required a lot of computing power. Therefore we were not able to cross-validate our results, as this would have drastically increased the computation time.

3.4 Reproduction of the Extrinsic Results

It was difficult to reproduce the extrinsic evaluation results of the papers. No detailed information was provided about the exact approach they used to rank the content. Our approach was to use the predicted labels from our own intrinsic evaluation, as the original results were not provided. Then we used a predefined implementation of Coordinate Ascent [Chen 2025] to rank the entries accordingly. As there was no information given on what features to use in the ranking, we had

to make educated guesses and try out different versions. One attempt was to match the queries to the titles and abstracts of all articles by using TFIDF-vectorization and use this similarity for the ranking algorithm. Another approach was to combine the proximity count with the BM25 ranking function [Robertson and Zaragoza 2009] and rank the entries based on this. Both of these approaches produce results that are far from the original paper.

As we could not gain further insights into the exact workflow, we were not able to reproduce the papers results in the extrinsic evaluation. The use of different data such as different predictions or entire datasets/query-sets to begin with could also have had a large influence here.

4 Results

In this section, we present the results of our reproduction of the original paper on the OSHUMED dataset.

4.1 Comparison of Results for the Intrinsic Evaluation

Table 1 shows our results for the intrinsic evaluation for the 5 defined metrics against the results of the paper. The LR results are very similar to those of the original paper. This is a good indication that our preprocessing pipeline captures the same nuances in the data as the original paper. Our DistilBERT model performed similarly to our LR model. However, in the paper, the DistilBERT model outperformed the LR model, although not very significantly.

Metric	Linear Regression		DistilBERT		Combined Approach	
	Paper	Our Impl.	Paper	Our Impl.	Paper	Our Impl.
Accuracy (%)	94.01	94.43	95.52	94.45	94.53	94.06
Precision (%)	76.72	76.62	82.75	77.47	74.61	72.15
Recall (%)	73.29	78.94	80.08	77.60	83.81	84.50
F1-Score (%)	74.96	77.77	81.39	77.53	78.94	77.84
F2-Score (%)	73.95	78.47	80.60	77.57	81.80	81.70

Table 1. Results for the Intrinsic Evaluation of the paper and ours for LR, DistilBERT and the combined approach (CA).

Table 2 shows the best model for each metric. Despite the F1 score, the best model for each metric matches those of the paper.

Metric	Best model (Paper)	Best model (Our Impl.)
Accuracy	DistilBERT	DistilBERT
Precision	DistilBERT	DistilBERT
Recall	Combined Approach	Combined Approach
F1-Score	DistilBERT	Combined Approach
F2-Score	Combined Approach	Combined Approach

Table 2. Metric and the respective model in which highest score was achieved

4.2 Comparison of Results for the Extrinsic Evaluation

Table 3 shows our results for the extrinsic evaluation for the post-filter and the joint-approach compared to those obtained in the paper. Our results are far off and far worse than those in the paper, suggesting large differences in the workflow and/or datasets. The paper did not provide confidence intervals or variance for these results.

Classifier	Post Filter		Joint Approach	
	Paper	Our Impl.	Paper	Our Impl.
LR	83.11	30.16	83.81	30.50
BERT	84.57	14.44	85.95	14.70

Table 3. Results for the Extrinsic of the paper and ours for LR and DistilBERT.

4.3 Statistical Relevance

Due to the lack of reported significance tests, confidence intervals, p-values, and variance in the original paper, we were unable to directly test whether our results differ significantly from theirs. The paper mentions that they performed McNemar’s test for intrinsic evaluation and a 5-fold cross-validation with a 2-tailed paired t-test for extrinsic results, but it does not specify how these tests were conducted. While they provided a significance level of 5%, no further statistical details were given.

To allow some form of statistical comparison, we adjusted the experimental setup by performing cross-validation on our logistic regression predictions. This allowed us to measure variation across folds and compute confidence intervals for all performance metrics. However, since the variation across our folds was very small, the confidence intervals were also narrow. This led us to conclude that all of our results were significantly different from those in the paper.

These findings should be interpreted with caution. Due to the lack of statistical detail in the original paper, we had to construct our own statistical framework, which may not be fully aligned with their methodology. A more ideal comparison would have required access to the paper’s per-fold results to directly conduct a paired t-test, the original classification outputs to replicate McNemar’s test, and a clearer description of their statistical approach to ensure comparability.

In addition, the cross-validation approach of estimating a distribution bears different caveats. While it poses as a suitable approach to retrieve different results to be able to calculate a possible standard deviation, it does not really reflect the conditions of the papers experiment. Further data points and possibly a distribution from the authors of the papers are needed to perform a proper statistical relevance analysis. For a Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test we would need results from cross validation from the paper itself to be able to compare it to our implementation.

Despite these limitations, our approach provides the best possible statistical estimate given the available information. This highlights the importance of transparent reporting of statistical measures in published research to enable direct and reliable comparisons. This approach was only conducted for logistic regression as running DistilBERT with cross validation would require a lot of computational power.

5 Discussion

In this study, we conducted a reproducibility analysis of the paper Comparing Intrinsic and Extrinsic Evaluation of Sensitivity Classification. The original paper proposed a hybrid approach using logistic

regression and DistilBERT for sensitivity classification. While we were able to replicate the results of the intrinsic evaluation with reasonable accuracy, several challenges arose due to missing details, such as unspecified random seeds and undocumented preprocessing steps. In addition, our study was limited to the OHSUMED dataset, as the Avocado dataset was not available.

Key hyperparameters were not fully disclosed in the original paper, requiring us to make informed assumptions. Despite this, our intrinsic evaluation results closely matched the original results, confirming the general validity of the approach. However, we encountered significant discrepancies in the extrinsic evaluation, largely due to the lack of transparency in the feature selection and ranking methodologies. These discrepancies suggest that either the data, the model outputs, or the ranking setup differed substantially from the setup in the paper.

The absence of statistical detail, including confidence intervals and significance tests, further complicated direct comparisons. While we attempted to mitigate this problem through cross-validation, such an approach is computationally expensive and may not fully reflect the original experimental setup. Our findings highlight the necessity for more comprehensive reporting in research to ensure true reproducibility. Specifically, providing precise implementation details, including random seeds, dataset versions, and statistical tests, would significantly improve the reproducibility of such studies. Our code is available at GitHub [al. 2025].

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Received 01 February 2025